

The first record of *Cyrtarachne finniganae* Lessert, 1936 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman

DSI/NRF Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda

ABSTRACT: The male of *Cyrtarachne finniganae* Lessert, 1936, was described from Mozambique and is here reported for the first time from South Africa. The female is still unknown. The general morphology of the male is discussed with notes on their distribution and lifestyle.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of Araneidae were sampled and photographed. In Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2023), a list of 120 Araneidae species have been listed on the South Africa National Spider List, including a single *Cyrtarachne* species. Since then, *C. termitophila* Lawrence, 1952, have been added to the list, and here *C. finniganae* Lessert, 1936 are recorded for the first time from South Africa.

The female is unknown, and the male is small and recognised by the wedge-shaped abdomen, the front legs metatarsi armed internally with numerous erect, spiniform setae arranged in a single row.

TAXONOMY

Cyrtarachne finniganae Lessert, 1936
Cyrtarachne finniganae Lessert, 1936

Diagnostic characters: Male 3 mm. Carapace as wide as long (Figs 1 & 3); narrower in eye region (Figs 1 & 6); anterior eye row viewed from the front strongly recurved; anterior median eyes larger than the posterior median eyes, their own diameter apart; posterior row recurved; lateral eyes closely grouped; sternum heart-shaped (Fig. 2). Abdomen large, broader than long, anteriorly sinuously arched; at the apex broadly rounded, yellowish, with black dorsal area darker; on sides two small, blunt, slightly raised and shining tubercles (Figs 1, 3, 6). Leg 1 with rows of short spinelike setae (Fig. 3). Male palp large as seen from below (Figs 4–5, 7). Female unknown.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA:

Gauteng: Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.71, 28.94). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.19, 30.33).

LIFESTYLE

Cyrtarachne species are known to construct “spanning thread webs” usually in low vegetation (Cartan & Miyashita, 2008). The specimens reported on here were sampled by sweeping grass in two reserves.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LOTZ L.N., BOOYSEN R., STEENKAMP R.C. & FOORD S.H. 2023. Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of South Africa. *African Invertebrates* 64(3): 221–289. <https://doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.64.111047151>.

Figures 1–7. *Cyrtarachne finniganae* 1–2. Habitus of juvenile from Ezemvelo Nature Reserve. 3. Line drawing male habitus. 4–5. Male palp. 6. Male from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve. 7. Male palp. Credits: 3–5. After Lessert (1936); 1–2 and 6–7. A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

CARTAN C.K. & MIYASHITA T. 2008. Extraordinary web and silk properties of *Cyrtarachne* (Araneae, Araneidae): a possible link between orb-webs and bolas. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 71(2): 219–235.

LESSERT, R. DE (1936). Araignées de l'Afrique orientale portugaise, recueillies par MM. P. Lesne et B.-B. Cott. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 43: 207–306. doi: [10.5962/bhl.part.144393](https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.part.144393)

WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2026. World Spider Catalog. Version 26. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 1 March 2026. doi: [10.24436/2](https://doi.org/10.24436/2)